

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of DL-methionine by quinolinium bromochromate

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Abstract : The oxidation of methionine (Met) by quinolinium bromochromate (QBC) in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) leads to the formation of corresponding sulphoxide. The reaction is of first order with respect to each QBC and Met. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of methionine was studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The solvent effect was analyzed by Kamlet's and Swain's multiparametric equations. Solvent effect indicated the importance of the cation-solvating power of the solvent. A suitable mechanism has also been postulated.

Keywords : Mechanism, quinolinium bromochromate, DL-methionine, chromium(VI).

Introduction

Pyridinium and quinolinium halochromates have been used as mild and selective oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹⁻⁴. Quinolinium bromochromate⁵ (QBC) is also one such compound. We have been interested in kinetics of oxidations by Cr^{VI} species and a few reports on oxidation by QBC have already been emanated from our laboratory⁶⁻⁸. In continuation of our earlier work on the oxidation studies by halochromates, we report here the kinetics of oxidation of DL-methionine by QBC in DMSO as solvent. A suitable mechanism has also been proposed.

Results and discussion

The oxidation of methionine by QBC resulted in the formation of the corresponding sulfoxides. The overall reaction may therefore, be represented as eq. (1).

QBC undergoes two-electron change. This is in accordance with the earlier observations with QBC.

The oxidation of Met, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce the polymerization of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile had no effect on the rate of oxidation (Table 1). Therefore, a one-electron

oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely. The reactions were found to be first order with respect to QBC. The reaction rate increases linearly with an increase in concentration of methionine (Table 1). The re-

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of methionine by QBC at 298 K

$10^3 [\text{BTEACC}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Met] (mol dm ⁻³)	[TsOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.00	0.10	0.00	1.41
1.00	0.20	0.00	2.75
1.00	0.40	0.00	5.53
1.00	0.60	0.00	8.30
1.00	0.80	0.00	11.1
1.00	1.00	0.00	13.5
2.00	0.20	0.00	2.86
4.00	0.20	0.00	2.52
6.00	0.20	0.00	2.79
8.00	0.20	0.00	2.78
1.00	1.00	0.10	15.3
1.00	1.00	0.20	17.5
1.00	1.00	0.40	22.0
1.00	1.00	0.60	26.1
1.00	1.00	0.80	30.9
1.00	1.00	1.00	35.7
1.00	0.40	0.00	5.67 ^a

^aContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters for the oxidation of Met by QBC

$10^4 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				ΔH^*	ΔS^*	ΔG^*
288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K	(kJ mol ⁻¹)	(J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	(kJ mol ⁻¹)
6.21	13.5	29.7	61.2	55.7 ± 0.5	-113 ± 2	89.3 ± 0.4

action is catalysed by hydrogen ions (Table 1). The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form: $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b[\text{H}^+]$. The experimental rate-law is as follows eq. (2).

$$\text{Rate} = k_1 [\text{Met}][\text{QBC}] + k_2 [\text{Met}][\text{QBC}][\text{H}^+] \quad (2)$$

The observed hydrogen-ion dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one acid-independent and another acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of QBC as (eq. 3) to yield a protonated Cr^{VI} species which is a stronger oxidant and electrophile.

The oxidation of Met was studied in nineteen organic solvents. There was no reaction with the chosen solvents. The kinetics are similar in all the solvents. The values of k_2 are recorded in Table 3. There is no significant correlation of the rate constants for oxidation, k_2 , in eighteen

Table 3. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of methionine by QBC at 298 K

Solvents	$10^5 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)	Solvents	$10^5 k_2$ (s ⁻¹)
Chloroform	50.1	Acetic acid	22.4
1,2-Dichloroethane	41.7	Cyclohexane	1.23
Dichloromethane	42.6	Toluene	9.12
DMSO	135	Acetophenone	48.9
Acetone	34.7	THF	18.2
DMF	72.4	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	20.0
Butanone	27.5	1,4-Dioxane	16.9
Nitrobenzene	55.0	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	11.2
Benzene	12.9	Carbon disulfide	4.57
Ethyl acetate	14.8		

solvents (CS₂ was not considered, as the complete range of the solvent parameters was not available) in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship equation of Kamlet *et al.*⁹. The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's equation¹⁰ of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents as well.

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (4)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the sol-

vent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (5) and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = 1.28 (\pm 0.03) A + 1.61 (\pm 0.02) B - 3.95$$

(5)

$$R^2 = 0.9969; \text{sd} = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.06$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.50 \pm 0.05 (A + B) - 3.96 \quad (6)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9838; \text{sd} = 0.06; n = 19; \psi = 0.13$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter¹¹.

The rates of oxidation of methionine in different solvents show an excellent correlation with Swain's equation with both the cation- and anion-solvating powers playing significant roles, though the contribution of the cation-solvation is slightly more than that of the anion-solvation. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 98% of the data. The observed solvent effect points to a transition state more polar than the reactant state. Further, the formation of a dipolar transition state, similar to those of S_N2 reactions, is indicated by the major role of both anion- and cation-solvating powers.

Mechanism :

The experimental results can be accounted for in terms of electrophilic oxygen transfer from QBC to the methionine-sulphur (eq. 7). The electrophilic attack on the sulphide-sulphur can be viewed as an S_N2 reaction. An S_N2 like transition state is supported by observed solvent effect also. The oxidation of methionine by QBC may involve a cyclic intermediate as has been suggested in many reactions of Cr^{VI}¹². The cyclic transition state will be highly strained in view of the apical position of a lone pair of electrons or an alkyl group. The formation of a cyclic transition state entails a more exacting specificity of orientation and should result in much larger negative entropy of activation than that observed.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

QBC was prepared by the reported method⁵ and its purity checked by an iodometric method. Methionine (Merck) was used as supplied. Due to non-aqueous nature of the solvent, toluene-*p*-sulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. Other solvents were purified by the usual methods¹³.

Product analysis : Product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. The oxidation of Met by QBC resulted in the formation of corresponding sulphoxide, which was determined by the reported method¹⁴. The yield of sulphoxide was $95 \pm 4\%$. The oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures i.e. after > 10 half-lives, as determined iodometrically, was +4.

Kinetic measurements : The pseudo-first order conditions were attained by maintaining a large excess ($\times 15$ or more) of the Met over QBC. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed, at constant temperatures (± 0.1 K), by monitoring the decrease in [QBC] spectrophotometrically at 365 nm. No other reactant or product has any significant absorption at this wavelength. The pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , was evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.990-0.999$) plots of $\log [\text{QBC}]$ against time for up to 80% reaction. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. All experiments, other than those for studying the effect of hydrogen ions, were carried out in the absence of TsOH.

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